

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

A COGNITIVE PERSPECTIVE ON THE DELIVERY OF AFFIRMATION IN STYLISTIC DEVICES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

The article approached the process of conveying affirmation of stylistic means from a cognitive aspect. It has been emphasized here that metaphor and metonymy are more important and different from stylistic means for cognitive linguistics. In cognitive linguistics, these devices are viewed as mental representations. In the article hyperbole, rhetorical questions, polysyndeton, etc. has been analyzed.

Keywords: Cognitive linguistics, stylistic devices, metaphor, mental representations

Introduction

Cognitive Linguistics is the study of language in its cognitive function, where cognitive refers to the crucial role of intermediate informational structures with our encounters with the world that our interaction with the world is mediated through informational structures in the mind. It is more specific than cognitive psychology, however, by focusing on natural language as a means for organizing, processing, and conveying that information. The main constituting feature of a stylistic device is the binary opposition of two meanings of the employed unit, one of which is normatively fixed in the language and does not depend upon the context, while the other one originates within certain context and is contextual. Nowadays it is impossible to answer the basic questions of linguistics without consideration of the principles underlying human cognitive activity. Scientists in cognitive linguistics have no doubt that language should be viewed as a system connected with other systems of knowledge, rather than as an isolated autonomous entity.

Main part. Cognitive linguistics is a branch of linguistics that focuses on how people perceive linguistic categories. In general, the main issue in cognitive linguistics is to try to study language within real language activity, taking into account the human factor. In linguistics and grammar, affirmativeness (affirmation) and negation is a means by which grammar transforms and transfers the positive and negative poles into verb combinations, sentences and statements. The affirmative (positive) form is used to express the authenticity or truth of the main claim, while the negative form indicates that it is false or incorrect. But in cognitive linguistics, this is a broader category. In grammar, we know the distinction between affirmative and negative sentences. According to the rules of grammar, all sentences can be negative or vice versa affirmative. But can all logically negated or affirmed sentences be true? It is not logically correct to deny the sentence *Everybody needs good health.*

The category of affirmativeness is expressed in lexical, grammatical and syntactic language stages. The main parts of speech belong to the identification core of

the affirmative category. Subgroup identification includes words represented by idioms, modal words, exclamations, lexemes, idioms, and phraseological structures. One of its means of expression is stylistic means. Stylistic means are also important in the delivery of affirmation. One of them, hyperbole, also creates a strong affirmative: *My grandmother is as old as the hills (My grandmother is very old)* [1].

Hyperbole is an emotional attitude of the speaker towards the object of discussion. However, it should be noted that not all exaggerations are stylistic devices. They are basically ready-made formulas created by a certain emotion in the spoken language. *Haven't seen you for ages! (Long time no see!)*. Like other stylistic devices, some hyperboles have lost their stylistic medium through frequent repetitions and have become a linguistic unit as a system. *A thousand pardons, to be dressed to kill*, etc.

Euphemisms are figuratively called "whitewashing device". Euphemisms meaning "nice talk" can also be means of affirmation. Here, too, the goal is to "lighten" the pronunciation of negative meanings. As a euphemism, the word "to die" was called "the journey's end" by Shakespeare and "that dreamsleep" by Byron.

Oxymorons, which are stylistic devices in linguistics, can also form strong affirmations in positive contexts.

Their Geography teacher was horribly beautiful means (Their geography teacher is very beautiful) [3].

Polysyndeton is a stylistic device with an abundance of conjunctions in the sentence. A conjunction purposefully serves to emphasize the connection between parts of a thought with the same characteristics, creating a rhythmic effect. *The heaviest rain, and snow, and hail, and sleet, could boast of the advantage over him in only one respect* [4].

Ellipsis should not be confused with elliptical sentences as a stylistic device. Elliptical sentences occur in laconic conversations.

Kate: Have a good weekend.

Tereca: Same to you. See you next week. But in the language of artistic works, ellipsis is used to emphasize the most important information by adding emotional

color. The simple verb news is shortened in parallel constructions in English to indicate the opposite feature of the phenomenon referred to. *His face was rather rugged; the cheeks thin (His face was very rough; his cheeks were thin).*

An epithet, as a figure of speech that expresses a permanent or transitory quality of a person or thing and characterizes it in terms of subjective perception, usually conveys an emotional meaning and can strengthen obvious affirmatives:

*Since my true love has forsaken me,
Marti'mas wind, when wilt thou blow
And shake the green leaves aff the tree?
Since my true love left me
Martimas wind, when will you blow
And will you shake the green leaves off the tree?*[2]

By the way, "rhetoric", a word of Greek origin, was the name given to the "teacher of the beauty of speech" in the ancient Greeks and Romans. The main purpose of the art of rhetoric is to be able to convince the listener about the truth of something. The importance of persuasion through the art of words can be seen from the oldest mythological works to the most modern works of literature. For example, in Homer's *Iliad*, masters of the art of words directed the Trojan War. The affirmative function is dominated by rhetorical questions, which also contain a hidden affirmation. Rhetorical questions are "unreal" questions, and the speaker does not actually expect the answer, or in other words, knows the answer to what he is asking. The question is actually stated here. In rhetorical questions, two syntactic meanings occur at the same time. Expresses questions and opinions. In our opinion, the main task of these types of sentences is to convey a message. Rhetorical questions are the communication of the author's thoughts or emotional response to the message being conveyed. It focuses on the falsification of denial and encourages the listener to make his own judgment. Thus, they reflect the thoughts of the speaker in the form of a message. It includes intonation, semantics and contextual particles. Some rhetorical questions are obvious because they discuss commonly known facts because the answer is suggested by the context. These kinds of rhetorical questions are also called rhetorical affirmations and are meant to emphasize a certain point. In Shakespeare's *The Merchant of Venice*, the character Shylock asks several rhetorical questions that are not directly addressed.

If you prick us, do we not bleed? If you tickle us, do we not laugh? If you poison us, do we not die? And if you wrong us, we shall not revenge? [5]

Rhetorical questions that do not need an answer stand in the middle between questioning and expressing an opinion. Although sometimes rhetorical questions seem pointless and unnecessary, they seem to be an essential need of everyday language, just as they are often used in fiction. Metaphor and metonymy are two main cognitive mechanisms of imagining. They are not figures of speech in cognitive linguistics, but "transfers" or "reflections" between conceptual models. The difference is that in metaphor the transfer is between differ-

ent experiential models. In metonymy, it occurs between the same cognition.

Paragons – Individuals represent ideals as category members. For example, Ronaldo is undoubtedly the best football player in the world, he is handsome, rich, kind. He is a good father and a successful football player. In other words, in most parts of the world, Ronaldo represents the paragon of football.

Mercedes is a luxury car and represents luxury. Chomsky is a prominent representative of generative linguistics. Paragons represent an entire category and set norms against other members of the category.

The explanation of metaphor for cognitive linguistics is very broad. Cognitive linguistics argues that metaphor is a central pervasive feature of human language and cognition. Metaphors allow traditional coding from sensorimotor domains to be used for cognitive pathways of subjective experience. Thus, the theory of conceptual metaphor explains how one idea or conceptual cognition can be understood under the terms of another. I. Richards noted in his work "Philosophy of Rhetoric" that "metaphor is not only a linguistic phenomenon, it is a way of thinking of a person" [6]. Inspired by Richards, J. Lakoff and M. Johnson tried to explain the metaphor from a new aspect. They presented metaphor as a conceptual phenomenon related to human thought and behavior.

In the conceptual approach, metaphors are transitions from a source cognitive pathway to a target cognitive pathway. Sometimes it preserves lexical encoding. According to Lakoff, "the most prominent feature of conceptual metaphors is that they preserve meaning". Love, anger are metaphorical concepts. Concepts specific to our perceptual system are time/quantity/situation/purpose/modality etc. understood through metaphors. These are concepts that normally include the grammaticalization of languages. If they are indeed metaphorical in nature, then metaphor becomes central to grammar. A feature of metaphor is the process by which we understand abstract concepts and carry out abstract reasoning.

Happy is up (Happiness is up, that is, flying from happiness. Here, the concept of happiness is connected with the meaning of "up" space). Metaphor is fundamentally conceptual, not linguistic [6]. Metaphorical language is the surface manifestation of a conceptual metaphor. Metaphorical understanding is based on non-metaphorical understanding. The conceptual metaphor system occurs automatically, involuntarily, and is used with imperceptible effort. Our metaphor system is central to understanding experience. Metaphor similes are more based on our experiences and play an important role in the grammar and lexis of the language.

Metaphorical encodings are universal, some are more widespread and some are culturally based. Virtually, the cognition in which human knowledge is formed is the human body, and this metaphor serves as the source domain. Common target domains are time, emotions and situations.

Consequently, the primary feature of affirmativeness in language should be understood in terms of cognitive coordination. Because affirmativeness is a linguistic category its coordinates are variable. It is closely

related to other linguistic categories. Affirmative action is subjective, epistemic, and speaker-centered. This category is multi-layered, graded and affects wide areas of language. More than any other paradigm, cognitive linguistics may better characterize this highly abstract phenomenon. We must take into account that a person's experience of the surrounding world is collected in his daily speech and emerges during the process of expressing his thoughts and cognition. Since affirmativeness is based on subjectivity, it should be noted that affirmativeness is well expressed by stylistic means, as stylistic means also express the inner subjective and emotional attitude of a person.

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